

Fertilizer management—organic

Effect of farmyard manure application on yield and soil fertility in rice - wheat rotation

B. S. Brar and N. S. Dhillon, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

We studied the effect of applying four graded levels of farmyard manure (FYM) (0, 10, 20, and 40 t/ha) on yield and soil fertility in a rice - wheat rotation. FYM was applied in a single dose in Jun 1989 or in four equal splits each June for 4 yr prior to transplanting rice (PR108) followed by wheat (HD2329). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Soil samples (0-15 cm depth) analyzed before starting the experiment showed that the Typic Ustochrept was sandy loam in texture, had pH of 8.3, and was nonsaline (EC 0.3 dS/m). Inorganic carbon content was low (6050 kg/ha) and bulk density was 1.52 Mg/m³.

Grain yield of both rice and wheat increased significantly with graded levels of FYM. The highest yield (6.7 t/ha) was obtained using 40 t FYM/ha over 4 yr in four equal splits (see table). The

Effect of FYM application on rice and wheat yields.^a

FYM applied ^b (t/ha)	Rice (t/ha)	Wheat (t/ha)
0	4.1	1.4
10*	4.2	1.6
10**	5.9	1.9
20*	4.5	1.9
20**	6.1	2.0
40*	5.0	1.7
40**	6.7	2.5
CD (P = 0.05)	0.7	0.4

^aAv of 4 yr. ^b* = applied in a single dose during Jun 1989. ** = applied in four equal splits to rice each year.

residual effect of lower levels of FYM (10-20 t/ha) on wheat yield was not significant. Average yield of rice and wheat was significantly more when FYM was applied in four equal splits than as a single application. The effect was more pronounced in rice; the residual effect on wheat yield was also conspicuous.

Soil organic carbon content improved with graded levels of FYM application from the initial value of 6050 kg/ha in Jun 1989 to 9600 kg/ha in May 1993 (see figure). Soil organic carbon content was highest where FYM was applied at 40 t/ha. It was significantly higher where

Organic carbon (1000 × kg/ha)

Organic carbon content of soil in May 1993 after 4 yr of experimentation, Ludhiana, India.

split doses of FYM were applied each year than where a single large application of FYM was made.

To maintain soil fertility at higher levels and to obtain higher rice and wheat yields, FYM should be applied to rice each year in splits rather than as a single large dose. ■

Crop management

Relationships between soil properties, crop and pest management practices, pest intensity, and crop performance in rainfed lowland rice

H. O. Pinnschmidt, IRRI; N. D. Long, University of Agriculture and Forestry (UAF), Thu Duc, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; P. Mekwatanakarn, Ubon Rice Research Center (URRC), P.O. Box 65, Muang, Ubon Ratchathani 34000, Thailand; T. T. Viet and L. D. Don, UAF, Vietnam; and P. S. Teng and A. Dobermann, IRRI

Holistic field surveys with integrated production level- and crop protection treatments were conducted at four rainfed lowland sites in northeast Thailand and in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, in 1992. At each site, 4-5 farmers' fields were subdivided into plots receiving either no pest control, pest control according to farmers' practices, or fungicide and insecticide applications 4-5 times during the growing season. Fields were visited repeatedly during the growing season to collect data on crop development, yield, dynamics of disease and pest severities, water conditions, physicochemical soil properties, and crop and pest manage-

ment practices. Descriptive analyses of the data were done.

Improved traditional varieties with superior grain quality prevailed in Thailand, while high-yielding IRRI varieties prevailed in Vietnam. Actual yields, final panicle numbers, and areas under the leaf area index progress curve were generally higher, while growth duration and plant height were shorter in Vietnam than in Thailand (Table 1). The data indicated more favorable physicochemical soil properties and much higher crop and pest management inputs in Vietnam than in Thailand. High incidence of drought was observed during the